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Study on Mental health status among Urban Adolescents

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Abstract

The current study was undertaken to assess the mental health status among urban adolescents. A total of 40 adolescents (20 females and 20 males) in the age group of 18- 21 years were selected as sample by using random sampling method. A standardized tool, Mental health assessment inventory developed by Jagadish and Srivastava (1995) was used to assess the mental health. Ex-post facto research design was adopted. The study was conducted at College of Community Science, Hyderabad, Telangana and Vaishnavi Degree College, Kurnool, Andra Pradesh. The results indicated that majority (68%) of the adolescents had average levels of mental health, while 18% had poor levels of Mental Health and only few (11%) reported good mental health status and it is also important to note that 3% of adolescents had very poor levels of mental health and none of the adolescents reported very good mental health status. It was also found that female adolescents reported better mental health status than male adolescents. Adolescents from joint families reported better mental health status than nuclear and extended families. Socio Economic Status had significant positive relationship with mental health status of adolescents at 1 % level. The study suggests that early detection and screening of mental health problems among adolescents is essential and addressing mental health issues by planning suitable intervention programmes to enhance mental wellbeing and quality of life among adolescents is imperative.

Key words: *Mental health, Adolescents, SES, Gender*

Mental health is a term used to describe emotional, psychological and social well-being. The quality of a person's mental health is often measured by how adaptively they can cope with everyday stressors. It encompasses how individuals think, feel and behave. It affects how individuals think, feel and behave, influencing their ability to cope with stress, maintain relationships, work productively, and make healthy choices. Persons with good mental health have the ability to cope with the normal stresses of life, work productively and contribute to society in a meaningful way. Thus, mental health is crucial for overall well-being and quality of life, persons with poor mental health suffers with mental

health related problems. Mental health disorders are common and can affect people of all ages, backgrounds and walks of life. Societal attitudes, public policies, and healthcare systems play crucial roles in addressing mental health needs.

Adolescence is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood and also a time of great change for young people where physical and psychological changes are happening at an accelerated rate. It is a period of storm and stress as many adolescents are young people who not only experience rapid physical and physiological changes, but also cognitive, social, emotional and interpersonal changes as well. As they grow and develop, their development gets influenced by outside factors, such as their environment, culture, religion, school and the media. Adolescence is period of identity formation. In Indian scenario majority of the adolescents adopt identity foreclosure where parents make decisions for their children about their educational and vocational choices. Regardless of adolescent's personal choice, they prefer to choose career option which is influenced by societal or parental expectations and is resulting in academic stress as well as various mental health related problems.

Adolescents with mental health issues are particularly vulnerable to social exclusion, discrimination, stigma, educational difficulties, risk-taking behaviours and physical ill-health. Globally, it is estimated that 1 in 7 (14%) of 10–19-year-olds experiencing mental health related problems and 1 in 10 (11.6%) adolescents ages between 18-24 years had serious behavioural or mental health difficulties yet remains underdiagnosed and undertreated (WHO, 2021). As per the National Mental Health Survey conducted by the National Institute of Mental Health and Neurosciences (NIMHANS), the prevalence of mental disorders including common mental disorders, severe mental disorders, and alcohol and substance use disorders (excluding tobacco use disorder) in adolescents over the age of 18 years is about 10.6%. Worldwide, it is estimated that 10%–20% of adolescents' had poor mental health conditions and contributing to 13% of the global burden of disease (Knopf 2008). Depression, anxiety, and behavioral disorders are among the leading causes of illness and disability in adolescents. Suicide is the fourth leading cause of death among individuals aged 15-29 years. All WHO Member States are committed to implementing the “Comprehensive mental health action plan 2013–2030”, which aims to improve mental health by strengthening effective leadership and governance, providing comprehensive, integrated and responsive community-based care, implementing promotion and prevention strategies, and strengthening information systems, evidence and research.

Urban adolescents often face unique stressors such as high academic pressure, socioeconomic disparities, peer pressure and exposure to violence or substance abuse. Research shows that mental health issues like anxiety, depression and behavioural disorders are prevalent among this demographic. Studying the mental health status of urban adolescents is essential for understanding the complexities

of adolescent development, addressing public health concerns, promoting health equity and informing evidence-based interventions and policies to support the well-being of youth in urban environments.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Location of the study

The current study was undertaken to study on Mental health status among urban adolescents. The study was carried out in College of Community Science, Hyderabad, Telangana and Vaishnavi Degree College, Kurnool, Andra Pradesh.

Research Design

Ex-post facto research design was adopted to study the Mental Health status of Urban Adolescents

Sample Size

The sample size comprised of 40 adolescents in the age group of 18-21 years out of which 20 were girls and 20 were boys.

Tools used for the study

Interview schedule was developed to know the general profile of the respondents that covers personal related information of the respondent such as Age, Gender, Birth Order, Educational Qualification, Family type. The Mental Health Inventory (MHI) scale developed by Jagdish and 68 Srivastava (1995) was used to find out the status of mental Health among adolescents. The scale has 56 items spread over six dimensions such as Positive Self Evaluation (PSE), Perception of Reality (PR), Integration of Personality (IP), Autonomy (AUNTY), Group oriented attitude (GOA) and Environmental competence (EC).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data was collected from adolescents to study their Mental health status. The demographic profile of the respondents is given in the table-1

Table:1 Distribution of the respondents based on Age (n=40)

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18	3	7.5
19	13	32.5
20	13	32.52
21	11	27.5

Fig 1: Age of the respondents

From the above table, it was observed that nearly one third of the respondents were in the age group of 20 years (33%), 19 years (32%) followed by 21 years (28%) and meagre percent (7%) were in the age group of 18 years.

Table: 2 Distribution of respondents based on Birth order

	Frequency	Percentage
1st Born	26	65
2nd Born	10	25
3rd Born	3	7.5
4th Born	0	0
5th Born	1	0.4

Fig 2 Birth Order of the respondents

Majority (65%) of the adolescents were first borns and one fourth of them were second borns (25%) and very few were later borns i.e. thrid borns (7.5%) followed by fifth borns (0.4%).

Table:3 Distribution of respondents based on Socio economic status (n=40)

Fig:3 Socio Economic Status of the respondents

Above half (52%) of the respondents belonged to upper middle SES category followed by lower middle SES category (25%). Few (18%) belonged to upper class and a meagre percent (5%) were in upper lower SES category.

Table:4 Distribution of respondents based on gender (n=40)

	Frequency	Percentage
Boys	40	100
Girls	40	100

Fig: 4 Gender of the respondents

Half of the respondents participated in the study were male and half of the respondents were females.

Table:5 Distribution of respondents based on Type of family (n=40)

Fig :5 Family type of the respondents

Majority (62.5%) of the respondents belonged to nuclear families followed by joint (22.5%) and extended (15%) families.

Table :1 Distribution of adolescents based on levels of dimensions of mental health (n=40)

S.no	Dimension of mental health	Levels of mental health					
		Good		Average		Poor	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1	Positive self-evaluation	2	5	26	65	12	30
2	Perception of Reality (PR)	6	15	24	60	10	25
	Integration of Personality (IP),	2	5	23	57.5	15	37.5
4	Autonomy (AUTNY)	4	10	25	62.5	11	27.5
5	Group oriented attitude (GOA)	2	5	31	77.5	7	17.5
6	Environmental competence (EC)	5	12.5	27	67.5	8	20

The above table depicts the status of urban adolescents in different dimensions. From the table 2, it can be interpreted that majority (65%) of the adolescents had medium levels of self-evaluation followed by low levels (30%) and meagre percent had high levels of self-evaluation. This indicates that to some extent majority of the adolescent girls and boys perceived themselves as positive such as they are worthy, capable and confident in different aspects of their life, sometimes they felt that they were resilient in facing of challenges, able to bounce back from setbacks, and maintain a positive outlook on life. It is also important to notice that nearly one third of the adolescents had negative self-perceptions about themselves like they are unworthy, not so confident and good at dealing with issues and challenges in their life. Adolescents often compare themselves with peers and influencers on social media, which results in poor self-image and low self-evaluation.

It was observed that majority (60%) of the respondents had medium levels of perception of reality, which indicates that to some extent they were able to understand events, situations and their own experiences based on the reality and it is also imperative to note that one fourth of the respondents were low level perception of reality which indicates that they had unrealistic, impractical and had more negative views about the real world experiences whereas few of them had right perceptions and good understanding of what is reality (15%). Adolescents lack the full cognitive maturity to perceive reality as fully as adults do leading to a sense of uncertainty about what is true or real, resulting in a moderate level of reality perception.

The table 2 also revealed that over half (58%) of the respondents had medium level of Integration of personality followed by low (38%) and a only a meagre percent (4%) had high levels of personality integration. This indicates that half of the adolescents were able to aware and accept their own strengths and weaknesses and other personality traits to some extent where as above two thirds were not much aware and accept about their own traits. Adolescents are in a phase of experimentation and self-discovery resulting in moderate integration of personality traits rather than a cohesive, fully integrated identity. Constant exposure to various lifestyles, ideals, and values through social media can create conflicting images of what adolescents "should" be, making it harder for them to consolidate their authentic self.

The findings also revealed that majority (62%) of the respondents had medium levels of autonomy followed by low level (28%) and very few (10%) had high level of Autonomy. It indicates that adolescents were able to make decisions independently by considering their own values and beliefs and had sense of self determination to some extent. Over one fourth of them had low sense of independence and poor self-determination.

In relation to group-oriented attitude, nearly eighty percent (78%) of the respondents had medium levels of group-oriented attitude and very few (18%) had low level and only meagre percent (4%) had high level. It means that most of adolescents perceived that they were empathetic, able to understand group dynamics and were able to make social interactions to some extent where as few of them were expressed unfavourable attitudes towards their social skills.

With regard to environmental competence, majority (67.5%) of the respondents had medium level of environmental competence whereas few had low level (20%) followed by high level (12.5%). This indicates that adolescents were able to adapt, cope with different situations, solve problems to some extent whereas few of them felt that they were not so efficient to adapt and function in their daily life. Very few felt that they were good at functioning and making adaptations.

Fig:6 Over all mental Health status of Adolescents

The figure 6 indicates the status of overall mental health among urban adolescents. The results revealed that over all mental health status was average among 68% of respondents, poor among 18 % and very poor among 3%. Only 11 % had good status of mental health and none of them had very good mental health status. This might be due to moderate followed by low level of positive self-image, environmental mastery, sense of independence, self-determination and group orientation skills. Keyes

(2006) indicated that youth ages from 15–18 years had moderate mental health. Green et al (2013) also indicated that nearly half (45.3%) of adolescents had mild/moderate mental and behavior disorders.

Table: 2 Gender differences in the dimensions of mental health among urban adolescents (n=40)

S.no	Dimension of mental health	Levels of mental health											
		Good				Average				Poor			
		Male		Female		Male		Female		Male		Female	
		F	%	f	%	f	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Positive self-evaluation	0	0	2	10	8	40	18	90	12	60	0	0
2	Perception of Reality (PR)	1	5	1	5	12	60	16	80	7	35	3	15
3	Integration of Personality (IP)	1	5	1	5	13	65	16	80	6	30	3	15
4	Autonomy (AUTNY)	1	5	2	10	10	50	14	70	9	45	4	20
5	Group oriented attitude (GOA)	2	10	2	10	11	55	17	85	7	35	1	5
6	Environmental competence (EC)	0	0	5	25	15	75	15	75	5	25	0	0

Fig:7 Gender differences in overall mental health status among urban adolescents

Figure 7 indicates that the overall mental health status was better among female adolescents than male adolescents. In the dimensions of self-evaluation, integration of personality, group-oriented attitude, autonomy and perception of reality female adolescents had better scores when compared to males. This indicates that adolescent girls had more positive perceptions about themselves such as being worthy, capable, empathetic and confident in maintaining good relationships and being cooperative with others, in meeting expectations of their friends, in making independent decisions as per their wishes when compared to adolescent boys. Similarly, Manchri *et al.* (2017) also revealed that female students had better mental health score than male. In line with the above Amerio *et al.* (2021) overall mental health was higher in proportions among females than males. In contrast, Van *et al.* (2018) found that scores of psychological distress, anxiety and depression were significantly high among girls than boys. Girls with poor social support experience mental health problems frequently than boys with strong social support. Along with these, Rajkumar *et al.* (2022) revealed social anxiety was found to be more prevalent among females when compared to males.

Table :3 Relationship between selected socio-demographic variables and Mental health of adolescents (n=40)

	Positive self-evaluation	Perception of Reality (PR)	Integration of Personality (IP)	Autonomy (AUTN Y)	Group oriented attitude (GOA)	Environmental competence (EC)	Overall Mental health
Age	-0.27	-0.19	-0.13	-0.37*	-0.12	-0.16	-0.29
Birth order	0.20	0.26	0.06	0.38*	0.03	-0.05	0.24
SES	0.47**	0.16	0.28	0.53**	0.33*	0.12	0.54**

*** Significance at 0.05 level and ** 0.01 level**

From the above table 3 it can be inferred that, age of the adolescent was significantly negatively correlated with dimension of autonomy. This indicates that as age increases autonomy decreases it can also be understood that younger adolescent had better in making independent decisions and had control over one's life when compared to older adolescents. This might be due to older adolescents had less freedom and more restrictions to act as per the own values and beliefs than younger adolescents. In line with the above finding Bastos *et al.* (2014) revealed that age was positively associated with mental health problems and Manchri *et al.* (2017) also stated that mental health and age was significantly negatively associated with each other.

Birth order has positive correlation with the dimension of autonomy. Later the birth order better was the mental health status. This indicates that later borns had better mental health when compared to first and second borns. This might be due to the reason that later borns experience less pressure, restrictions, more freedom to explore and develop their own identities than first and second borns.

Whereas Easey *et al.* (2019) indicated that higher birth order was associated with an increased risk of suicide and psychiatric disorder. Chandola (2016) indicated that oldest born have more psychiatric than the other groups. Pruckner *et al.* (2019) stated that first born children are more likely to consume medical drugs and to utilize medical services.

SES was positively significantly correlated with Group oriented attitude at 5% level, autonomy and overall mental health at 1 % level. Which indicates that higher the Socio- economic status better the autonomy, positive self-evaluation and group orientation attitudes. It can also be inferred that adolescent from high socio-economic status had better independence, favourable attitudes on group interactions and positive self-image than adolescents from low SES back ground. This might be due to the reason that high socio- economic status provides more access to education, resources and opportunities, freedom to make one's own choices and control over environmental circumstances and less financial instabilities and worries. Similarly, Tao *et al.* (2015) revealed that parents with higher education are better equipped with knowledge and various approaches to provide preventive measures to reduce anxiety and depression in children. Villadsen (2018) also stated that students whose parents had higher occupation had better mental health as compared to students with lower occupation. Apart from these Yang *et al.* (2021) found that mental health was positively associated with parents' education and lower SES.

Conclusion

From the above study it can be concluded that, majority of the urban adolescents had average levels of mental health. Followed by poor and good levels of mental health. Age was significantly negatively correlated with dimension of autonomy. Birth order has positive correlation with the dimension of autonomy. SES was positively significantly correlated with dimensions of PSE, autonomy, GOA and overall mental health. Hence, addressing mental health concerns is essential for promoting holistic development and resilience. The study suggests that early detection and screening of mental health problems among adolescents is essential and addressing mental health issues by planning suitable intervention programmes to enhance mental wellbeing and quality of life among adolescents is imperative. Parents should provide congenial home environment since childhood to enhance autonomy among the adolescents. It is essential for policymakers, educators, healthcare professionals and communities to collaborate in implementing evidence-based interventions and fostering a culture that prioritizes mental well-being for all adolescents. Media should propagate on the early symptoms of mental health related problems among adolescents and measures to enhance status of wellbeing.

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